

Annex

ePOCT+ Rwanda: a clinical decision support algorithm for managing sick children below 15 years of age in primary healthcare settings

1. Older child algorithm (2 months to 14 years) pages 2-94
2. Young infant algorithm (< 2 months) pages 95-109
3. Drugs linked to diagnoses page 110-116
4. Drug formulations page 117-121

Disclaimer: These representations of the algorithm are for reference of scope and content only. There can be discrepancies between these diagrams and the actual programming of the algorithm because draw.io representations are not machine readable and hence open to interpretation. Furthermore, the algorithm has been undergoing continuous minor adaptations throughout the implementation of the DYNAMIC project. If intended for implementation, further information and explanations, as well as machine readable content of the most up-to-date algorithm, can be provided upon request.

1. Older child algorithm (2 months to 14 years)

Visit Flow

EMERGENCY PAGE: Accessible at any point during consultation

This 'emergency button' can be accessed at any point in the consultation without requiring the user to enter registration details or answer multiple questions - for critical cases requiring immediate management.

*Shock / severe dehydration: Weak pulse, cold extremities, cap. refill >3sec, very slow skin pinch)

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC0 General / Universal Assessment (Algorithms developed in all)

* Emergency signs include: Convulsions, unconscious, lethargic, stiff neck; Priority signs: History of fever, measured fever
 **Also evaluated in CC neurological problem (Suspicion of meningitis)
 ***Severe comorbidities/complications: CNS Danger signs, Severe anemia, severe dehydration, measles or complicated measles, complicated chicken pox, respiratory distress, bacterial/IMCI/IMAI pneumonia, fail appetite test

ACT: Artemisinin-based combination therapy
 CC: Complaint Category
 CNS: Central Nervous System
 Hb: Hemoglobin
 IM: Intra-muscular
 m: month
 MUAC: Mid-Upper Arm Circumference
 PO: per os
 WAZ: Weight-for-Age Z-score
 WFH: Weight-for-Height Z-score
 y: year

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC1 Respiratory problem (Assessed in all within CC0 General / Universal Assessment)

*Fast breathing: Respiratory rate 75-96%ile
 ** If no CRP available, use IMCI/IMAI respiratory thresholds: 2-12m >=50/min, 12-59m >=40/min, 5-12y >=30/min, 12-14y >=20/min
 *** Or possibility of swallowing foreign object in airways
 INH BD: Inhaled bronchodilator (most often salbutamol)
 CS: Corticosteroids
 TB: Tuberculosis

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC2 Ear, Nose, Mouth and Throat Problem

*Cape Town CDR score:
 1 point: Absence of rhinorrhea, absence of cough, tonsillar exudate
 2 points: Tonsillar swelling

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC3 Eye problem

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC4 Skin and hair problem

*Anaphylaxis : Urticaria AND (CNS Danger signs or Severe abdominal pain or Difficulty breathing or Vomiting)

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC5 Gastrointestinal problem

*Excessive diarrhea or vomiting = >=4 stools or emesis/24hrs for age 2m-12m, >=5 stools or emesis for age 1-5y, >= 6 stools or emesis for age 5-14y
 **Excessive diarrhea and vomiting = >=3 stools and emesis/24hrs for age 2m-12m, >=4 stools and emesis for age 1-5y, >= 5 stools and emesis for age 5-14y
 ***Oral fluid challenge: Provide water to drink and see if able to drink without vomiting. Pass = able to drink. Fail = Not able to drink
 ORS: Oral Rehydration Salt

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC6 Urine/Genital problems

CC6: Uro-genital problems

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC7 Neurological problems

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC8 Trauma, accidents, burns, pain, wounds

CC8: Trauma, accidents, burns, pain, wounds

MEDICAL ASSESSMENT : CC9 Prevention

CCO: General assessment/CC1: Respiratory problem

- Cough OR
- Difficult breathing

- Runny nose AND
- NO Danger signs

Danger Signs Respiratory Distress
 - Tachypnea $\geq 97^{\text{th}}$ ile AND Chest indrawing, OR
 - Tachypnea $\geq 97^{\text{th}}$ ile AND Patient unable to finish sentence due to difficult breathing (children 5-14 years), OR
 - SaO₂ < 90%, OR
 - Grunts, OR
 - Severe difficult breathing needing referral

YES	NO
-----	----

- Tachypnea $> 75^{\text{th}}$ ile OR
 - Lower chest indrawing OR
 - Fever ≥ 4 days

YES	NO
-----	----

(Difficulty breathing OR Cough) AND
 (Tachypnea $> 75^{\text{th}}$ ile OR Chest indrawing) AND Wheezing

YES	NO
-----	----

Significant hemoptysis
 (>1 episode, not associated with nose bleed or lesion in mouth, not vomiting blood)

Fever, AND
 NO CNS Danger signs

Improvement after bronchodilator

CRP test

$\geq 40\text{mg/L}$ OR $\geq 10\text{mg/L}$ (in those with severe comorbidities*)	$< 40\text{mg/L}$ OR $< 10\text{mg/L}$ (in those with severe comorbidities*)
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Severe Pneumonia
 - Antibiotics
 - **Oxygen therapy regardless of SpO₂**
 - INH BD if presence of wheezing
 - Refer

Bacterial Pneumonia
 - Antibiotics
 - No referral

Viral Pneumonia
 - No antibiotics
 - No referral

Cough or cold
 - No antibiotics
 - No referral

Reactive Airway Disease
 - INH BD
 - No referral

Hemoptysis
 - Refer for investigations

*Severe comorbidities: Uncomplicated Severe Acute malnutrition, < -3 z-scores weight for age, cerebral palsy, sickle cell disease, HIV, Severe anemia, Congenital heart disease
 INH BD: Inhaled bronchodilator (most often salbutamol)

CCO General

Anthropometric measures						
= < - 3 z-score for WFA or WFH/L	< 11.5 cm MUAC or < -3 z-score for WFH/L	< - 3 z-score for MUAC for age	< - 3 z-score for WFA	-2 z-score for WFA or WFH	11.5 - 12.5 cm MUAC	-2 z-score for MUAC for age
2m - 5m	6m - 59m	5y - 14y	6m - 10y	2m - 59m	6m - 59m	5y - 14y

Complication criteria
Chickenpox lesions OR
Measles rash and associated signs OR
(cough or difficulty breathing AND fast breathing) OR
Presence of a severe diagnosis OR
Severe Croup OR
Suspicion of foreign object in airways OR
Severe Persistent Diarrhea OR
Severe malaria OR
Severe anemia OR
Complicated prolonged fever OR
Mastoiditis OR
IMCI severe anemia OR
Suspicion of meningitis OR
Severe abdominal condition OR
Severe eye disease OR
Complicated abscess OR
Complicated cellulitis OR
Osteomyelitis/Septic arthritis OR
Severe dehydration OR
Severe pneumonia OR
Danger signs OR
Fail appetite test OR
Child too sick to perform test
(Appetite test unavailable AND Caregiver reports not feeding well) OR
Bilateral feet edema

YES

NO

Complicated Severe Acute Malnutrition

- Antibiotics (Ampi/Genta)
- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Prevent hypothermia
- Referral for urgent care

Uncomplicated Severe Acute Malnutrition

- Antibiotics in children <5 years
- Non-urgent referral (within 3 days) for malnutrition follow-up / assessment and RUTF
- Vit A if xerophthalmia/night blindness

Very Low Weight-for-Age

- Antibiotics (if febrile and <5 years)
- Non-urgent referral for malnutrition follow-up / assessment and RUTF
- Vit A if xerophthalmia/night blindness

Moderate Malnutrition

- No antibiotics
- Non-urgent referral for malnutrition follow-up / assessment
- Vit A if xerophthalmia/night blindness

BMI: Body Mass Index
 MUAC: Mid-Upper Arm Circumference
 RUTF: Ready-to-Use Therapeutic Food
 WFA: Weight for Age
 WFH/L: Weight-for-Height or Weight-for-Length

CC0 General

Hb available?

Yes | No

Reasons to perform Hb

- Diarrhea > 14 days
- HIV positive
- Danger signs
- Respiratory distress
- Moderate malnutrition
- Severe malnutrition
- Very Low Weight For Age
- Sickle Cells Disease
- Jaundice
- Conjunctival OR palmar pallor

- Fever if age <5 y

conjunctival or palmar pallor

Severe | Some

Hemoglobin

< 6 g/dL	< 7 g/dL	6-9,5 g/dL	6-10,5 g/dL	7-11 g/dL	7-11,9 g/dL
Age	Age	Age	Age	Age	Age
2m - 59m	5y - 14y	2m - 6m	6m - 59m	5y - 11y	12y - 14y

Severe Anemia

- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Refer

Mild / moderate Anemia

- Iron supplementation (if fever, wait until end of febrile illness. No iron supplementation if already on RUTF or if presence of Sickle cell disease)
- folic acid
- No referral
- Follow up in 14 days

Non urgent referral if already on iron for > 2m then

If concern for **Hemolytic anemia** (pallor AND jaundice)

- Non urgent referral for investigations
- NO Iron or Folate

deworming : see specific algorithm

Severe IMCI Anemia

- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Refer

Mild / moderate Anemia

- Iron supplementation (if fever, wait until end of febrile illness. No iron supplementation if already on RUTF or if presence of Sickle cell disease)
- folic acid
- No referral
- Follow up in 14 days

Non urgent referral if already on iron for > 2m then

If concern for **Hemolytic anemia** (pallor AND jaundice)

- Non urgent referral for investigations
- NO Iron or Folate

deworming : see specific algorithm

**CC0 Universal
Assessment /
General**

CC0 Universal Assessment / General

Fever

If age $\geq 12m$ to 60m :
Stiff neck

Unable to drink or breastfeed

Vomiting everything, AND < 5years

Fail Oral rehydration challenge

Very severe febrile disease

- Ampicillin+Gentamicin
- Diazepam (if convulsing now)
- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Antipyretic if fever
- Refer

CC7 Neurological manifestations

Age \geq 5y

- Fever, AND
- NO CNS Danger sign, AND
(Headache, OR Neck pain or stiffness)

Stiff neck

Suspicion of meningitis
- Ampicillin+Gentamicin
- Prevent low blood sugar
- Refer

CC5: GI problem

CC0: Universal assessment

¹ Age adapted vomiting and diarrhea:
 Age 2-12m: >= 4 loose stools or >=4 episodes of vomiting / 24hours, or >=3 loose stools/24 hours and vomiting
 Age 12 - 59m: >=5 loose stools or >=5 episodes of vomiting / 24 hours, or >=4 loose stools/24 hours and vomiting
 Age 5 - 14y: >=6 loose stools or >=6 episodes of vomiting / 24 hours, or >=5 loose stools/24 hours and vomiting
²Oral rehydration challenge: Provide water to drink and see if able to drink without vomiting (observe for 2 hours).
³Antibiotics (Ciprofloxacin) for children < 5 years. If >=5 years, antibiotics only if febrile, or < -3 z-score for MUAC for age
 ORS: Oral Rehydration Salt

CCO: General / Universal Assessment

Fever

--- No source of fever

- NO Cough
- NO difficult breathing
- NO runny or blocked nose
- NO Loose or liquid stools (diarrhea)

PS: NO Eye source of fever

Eyelid oedema OR
Warm tender swelling around eye

PS: NO ENT Source of fever

Neck mass
OR
(Sore throat AND age >=36m)
OR
Ear pain OR ear discharge
OR
(tooth pain AND dental abscess)
OR
(Cheek swelling AND Suspicion of mumps)

PS: NO Skin rash source of fever

Measles rash and associated signs
OR
Chickenpox lesions
OR
Scarlet fever rash
OR
Cellulitis
OR
Abscess
OR
Impetigo
OR
Bullous Impetigo
OR
Ecthyma lesion

PS: NO Musculoskeletal source of fever

(Musculo-skeletal pain or swelling (bone or joint pain/swelling) OR Limping OR Refusal (unable) to move extremity) AND Warm, tender or swollen joint or bone

PS: NO Urogenital source of fever

Age >=36 m AND pain or difficulty urinating
OR
Age >12y AND Female AND History of sexual contact AND lower abdominal pain AND Abnormal vaginal discharge AND lower abdominal tenderness

NO Identifiable Source of Fever

The patient has fever, but none of the following symptoms:

- Cough/difficult breathing
- Diarrhea/loose stools
- ear pain/discharge
- dental pain/abscess
- sore throat
- neck mass
- skin rash explaining the fever (chicken pox, measles, scarlet fever, cellulitis, abscess, impetigo)
- bone or joint pain suspicious of septic arthritis/osteomyelitis
- symptoms of urinary tract infection or STI

Is there an explanation for the fever?

CRP

>=40mg/L	<40mg/L	No CRP*
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mRDT or malaria microscopy

Positive	Negative	Unavailable
----------	----------	-------------

Age

< 3 months	3m - 24m	2y - 14y
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Age

2m - 24m	2y - 14y
----------	----------

Urinalysis

Positive	Negative / unavailable
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Well appearing (1 hour after paracetamol)

Yes	No
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Fever without source: Presumed bacterial infection

- TT Amoxicillin HD and Ciprofloxacin
- No referral
- Plan A: Home rehydration
- Refer Urgently if unexplained bleeding (concern for hemorrhagic fever)
- COVID-19 counselling

Febrile urinary Tract Infection

- TT Ciprofloxacin
- No referral

Fever without source: Presumed viral infection

- Symptomatic treatment
- No referral
- Refer Urgently if unexplained bleeding (concern for hemorrhagic fever)

CC0 General

- Fever, OR
- 1 >= convulsions, OR
- Unconscious, OR
- Lethargic

mRDT
(Microscopy if mRDT not available)

Positive	Negative	Unavailable
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Severity criteria

PS: Respiratory distress

Cough
OR Difficulty breathing) AND (Chest Indrawing OR Fast breathing Age-specific)
AND Blood oxygen saturation <90%
OR
Difficulty breathing AND (grunting OR severe difficult breathing needing referral)

PS: GI Danger Signs

Unable to drink or breastfeed	Vomiting everything, AND < 5years
↓	
Fail Oral rehydration challenge	

Unconscious or Lethargic
Convulsing now
Convulsions in present illness
Severe anemia (age specific cutoff) OR Clinical Severe anemia (Hb unavailable)
Jaundice

1 or more	0
-----------	---

Severity criteria

PS: Respiratory distress

Cough
OR Difficulty breathing) AND (Chest Indrawing OR Fast breathing Age-specific)
AND Blood oxygen saturation <90%
OR
Difficulty breathing AND (grunting OR severe difficult breathing needing referral)

PS: GI Danger Signs

Unable to drink or breastfeed	Vomiting everything, AND < 5years
↓	
Fail Oral rehydration challenge	

Unconscious or Lethargic
Convulsing now
Convulsions in present illness
Severe anemia (age specific cutoff) OR Clinical Severe anemia (Hb unavailable)
Jaundice

1 or more	0
-----------	---

Severe malaria

- IM artesunate
- IM Ampicillin/Gentamicin
- Refer to DH with blood slides

Uncomplicated malaria

- PO artemether-Lumefantrine
- No referral
- if vomiting or diarrhea treat with 1st line: IM Artesunate / 2nd line IV quinine
- Daily visit :
 - if improvement --> switch to oral
 - in no improvement --> refer
- Consider admitting the patient if outpatient management impossible due to transportations constraints/social issues

Clinical Severe malaria

- IM artesunate
- IM Ampicillin/Gentamicin
- Refer

Suspected malaria

- Refer for malaria test

Suspected malaria

- PO artemether-Lumefantrine
- No referral
- if vomiting or diarrhea treat with 1st line: IM Artesunate / 2nd line IV quinine
- Daily visit :
 - if improvement --> switch to oral
 - in no improvement --> refer
- Consider admitting the patient if outpatient management impossible due to transportations constraints/social issues

Artesunate doses :	
Individuals ≥20 kg: 2.4 mg/kg intravenously (first dose)	
Individuals <20 kg: 3 mg/kg intravenously (first dose)	

Transfer to nearby clinic with mRDT test possible within 2 hours?

YES	NO
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*Significant weight loss = Poor weight gain, failure to thrive, documented weight loss

CC0 General

Fever

Fever duration
>=7 days

Severity criteria

PS: Severe comorbidity

Very Low Weigh for Age

Severe Acute Malnutrition

HIV positive

Cerebral palsy

Severe anemia

Sickle cell disease

Congenital heart disease

OR

- Fever >=14 days

Yes

No

mRDT

Positive

Negative

Complicated prolonged fever

- No ATB
- Refer

Prolonged fever

- No ATB
- Referral for further investigations within 3 days

CC2 Ear, Nose, or Throat problem

Age 3 - 14y

Sore throat and tonsillar swelling

Cape Town clinical decision rule

- Tonsillar swelling (2 points)
- Tonsillar exudate (1 point)
- Absence of cough (1 point)
- Absence of rhinorrhea (1 point)

≥ 3 points

< 3 points

Bacterial pharyngitis

- Antibiotics (Amoxicillin PO)
- No referral
- Ibuprofen

Viral pharyngitis

- No antibiotics
- No referral
- Ibuprofen

*Severe comorbidities: Uncomplicated Severe Acute malnutrition, <-3 z-scores weight for age, cerebral palsy, sickle cell disease, HIV, Severe anemia, Congenital heart disease

*Severe abdominal palpation needing referral =
Diffuse rebound tenderness. Pain to even light touch.
Specific signs of appendicitis: Right lower quadrant tenderness or rebound tenderness, accentuated when jumping on right foot, pain migrating from the umbilical region associated with fever.

CC2 Ear, Nose, or Throat problem

COVID-19 guidance:

The patient is presenting signs and symptoms compatible with COVID-19. Patients with suspected COVID-19 should be isolated to contain virus transmission (especially to vulnerable populations). Please follow local guidelines in order for the patient to be referred to a designated COVID-19 health facility, community facility or at home (self-isolation). Antibiotics are not recommended for treatment or prophylaxis for patients with mild or moderate COVID-19 (unless there is clinical suspicion of a bacterial infection). Of note, few patients with COVID-19 experience a secondary bacterial infection.

- If the patient will be self-isolated at home, the following recommendations should be followed:
- Place the patient in a well-ventilated single room (ideally in a different room from others)
 - Limit movement of the patient in the house and minimize shared space (keep windows open) if sharing space.
 - Wash hands after any type of contact with the patient or their immediate environment.
 - A mask should be worn as much as possible by the patient.
 - Caregivers should wear a mask when in the same room as the patient.
 - Avoid direct contact with body fluids (oral respiratory secretions, and stool).
 - Avoid sharing potentially contaminated items (toothbrushes, eating utensils, towels, bed linen, washcloths, clothes)

Advise close contacts of the patient that they are at risk of contracting COVID-19, and must seek care if they develop symptoms and wear face masks and wash hands.

Special attention must be given to limit transmission to vulnerable close-contacts, such as those with chronic diseases (hypertension, diabetes, HIV), and the elderly (>= 60 years).

Return to clinic in case there are worsening symptoms (especially dyspnea)

REF: WHO/2019-nCov/IPC/HomeCare/2020.3

Suspicion of foreign object in airways
 Refer urgently with caretaker for inpatient management.
 If referral is not possible, manage the child as described in the national guidelines or WHO Pocket Book for hospital care for children.

Severe Croup

- Prednisolone PO
- Avoid agitation
- Referral if no improvement after one hour on Prednisolone or Dexamethasone

Mild Croup

- Croup counseling
- No referral
- Return to clinic if worsening symptoms

CC2 Ear, Nose,
Mouth or Throat
problem

Tooth Pain

Dental abscess

YES	NO
-----	----

Dental Abscess

- If fever : Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid
- Paracetamol
- Dental abscess drainage and incision
- Mouthwash with antiseptic
- Non urgent referral

Tooth pain

- Paracetamol
- Non urgent referral

For cost reasons
1st line in Rwandan HC is
Amoxicillin+Metronidazole

CC2 Ear, Nose, or Throat problem

age 2m-5y

Foreign body in ear

- Removal of object not possible, OR
- Object not visible

Foreign body in ear
- Removal of object
- Ciprofloxacin ear drops
(if lesion in ear after
removal)
- No referral

Foreign body in ear
- Refer for outpatient
management: ENT

CC2 Ear, Nose, or Throat problem

- Mouth pain, OR
- Poor feeding, OR
- Sore throat

- Physical exam:
- Mouth ulcers, OR
 - Herpangina

Oral aphtous ulcers

- Oral aphtous ulcers advice
- Paracetamol
- Gentian violet (half strength)
- No referral

CC2 Ear, Nose, or Throat problem

- White plaques in the mouth, OR
- Poor feeding

- Physical exam finding:
- White plaques in the mouth

Oral Candidiasis

- Nystatin suspension
- Symptomatic counselling
- If HIV or moderate or severe malnutrition or failed treatment with nystatin : Fluconazole PO
- No referral

CC2 Ear, Nose,
Mouth or Throat
problem

Runny nose

Common cold

- URTI Symptomatic care*
- No antibiotic
- No referral
- Refer if 5 days without improvement

*Soothe the throat and relieve the cough with a safe remedy, such as tea with lemon, lime, or honey.-
Drink fluids: Fluids keep the throat moist and prevent dehydration.- Clear secretions from child using a
cloth soaked in water that has been twisted to form a pointed wick(Adapted from IMCI 2014, and Mayo
Clinic 2020)

CC3 Eye

- Red eye, AND
- Eye trauma/foreign body in eye

Corneal abrasion

- Foreign body removal from the eye
- Chloramphenicol 0.5% eye drops
- Refer if removal of foreign body not possible

CC3 Eye

- Clouding of cornea, OR
- Severe eye pain, OR
- Bleeding of eye, OR
- Red eye > 2 weeks, OR
- In-turned eye lashes

Severe eye disease
-Refer

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Abscess : red elevated skin lesion/bump, painful and sometimes associated with fever. It is full of pus

- Abscess size >5 cm (unless peri-anal), OR
- Abscess location face, OR
- Large surrounding cellulitis (warm, red, tender) around abscess

No	Yes
----	-----

Simple abscess

- Abscess care, general (including drainage)
- Abscess car guidance
- Paracetamol
- If drainage not possible : erythromycin
- No referral

Complicated abscess

- Abscess care, general (including drainage)
- Erythromycin
- Paracetamol
- Refer if drainage not possible

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Cellulitis : warm, red, tender

- No regression of skin lesion despite 72hrs of antibiotic treatment, OR
- Cellulitis location face, OR
- Severe pain around skin lesion, OR
- lethargic or unconscious, OR
- Skin lesion size \geq 2x patients' palm

No

Yes

Uncomplicated cellulitis

- 1st line : Ampicillin + Cloxacillin PO | 2nd line co-amoxicillin
- Paracetamol
- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- No referral

Complicated cellulitis

- 1st line : Ampicillin + Cloxacillin PO | 2nd line co-amoxicillin
- Paracetamol
- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- Refer

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Other skin lesion

- Impetigo : honey colored crusted lesion, OR
- Bullous Impetigo : fragile, flacid bullae with yellow fluid, OR
- Ecthyma lesion : Ulcer covered with yellow crust. Sometimes ulcer with necrotic black eschar

- Lesion size > 1x patient's palm, OR
- Fever

No

Yes

Uncomplicated Impetigo

- Potassium Permanganate solution | 2nd line: Chlorerexidine solution
- Paracetamol
- Skin hygiene precautions
- No referral

Complicated Impetigo

- Antibiotics = 1st line: Ampicillin + Cloxacillin PO | 2nd line: erythromycin PO
- Desinfectant = 1st line: Potassium Permanganate solution | 2nd line: Chlorerexidine solution
- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- Skin hygiene precautions
- No referral

Rwanda Dermatology Clinical Treatment Guideline suggest topic antibiotic (fucidic acid). However, there is concern for selection of *S. aureus* resistant strains

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Chicken pox lesions
- multiple lesions of different stages : macules, papules, vesicles, crusted papules, may also be present on hairy scalp/genitals. Almost always very itchy, often associated with headache and diffuse muscle pain

- HIV, OR
- <-3 z-score weight for age, OR
- <-3 z-score MUAC for age in children 5-14 years
- MUAC < 11.5cm, OR
- Cough or difficulty breathing AND Respiratory distress, OR
- Cellulitis (warm, red, tender), OR
- Lower chest indrawing AND cough or difficulty breathing, OR
- Tachypnea \geq 75th percentile AND cough OR difficulty breathing

No

Yes

Uncomplicated Chickenpox

- Calamine lotion
- Paracetamol
- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- Skin hygiene precautions
- No referral

Complicated Chickenpox

- Calamine lotion
- Paracetamol
- Acyclovir PO
- Refer

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Other skin lesion

Oral Herpes : Single or grouped vesicles, often around mouth. Often painful

No Impetigo : honey colored crusted lesion (confirm with photo)

Herpes simplex - Oral lesions (herpes labialis)

- Paracetamol
- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- Skin hygiene precautions
- If HIV or malnutrition : Acyclovir PO
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Tinea Corporis :
Often itchy circular or oval red scaling patch or plaque. At later stages central clearing occurs, with spread of raised borders. It is sometimes surrounded by vesicles

Extensive skin disease

No

Yes

Tinea Corporis

- 1st line: Clotrimazole cream 1 or 2% (skin) | 2nd line: Benzoic acid
- No referral

Generalized (extensive) Tinea Corporis

- 1st line: Griseofluvin | 2nd line: fluconazol
- HIV test
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Tinea Capitis :
Often itchy circular or oval red scaling patch or plaque, sometimes surrounded by vesicles, pustule formations or a buggy fluctuant mass (kerion). It is often associated with hair loss

Tinea Capitis

- Antifungals = 1st line:
Griseofulvin | 2nd
line: Fluconazol
- Ketoconazol shampooing
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Scabies :
Itchy (especially at night), small, red papules or vesicles, sometimes with excoriation or scabietic burrows. Found mostly in interdigital spaces of the hands and feet, wrists, waistline, and genitals. In infants consider palms and soles

Scabies

- Benzyl benzoate 25% emulsion | 2nd line
- Permethrin 5% cream
- Antihistaminic (Claritin 10 mg 5 days)
- Paracetamol
- Scabies household management advice
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Urticaria:
Raised, red plaques, often appearing and enlarging very fast. Very itchy, especially at night

- Danger sign, OR
- Difficult breathing, OR
- Vomiting, OR
- Severe abdominal pain

No

Yes

Urticaria

- Age \geq 6 months : Cetirizine hydrochloride PO
- No referral

Anaphylaxis

- Epinephrine (adrenaline) IM
- Age \geq 6 months : Cetirizine hydrochloride PO
- Refer

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Atopic eczema:
Itchy, thick (lichenified) plaques (sometimes hypo or hyperpigmentation especially on dark skin), in flexural surfaces especially elbows, knees, neck, wrist, and ankles. Rarely in groin and axilla region

Eczema (Atopic dermatitis)

- Antiseptic = Potassium permanganate
- Emollients = aqueous cream | plain vaseline
- Dermocorticoids = 1st line: Hydrocortisone cream | 2nd line: betamethasone cream
- Eczema guidance
- No referral

L'enfant a-t-il de la fièvre ?
(Antécédent ou corps chaud au toucher ou température de 37.5 °C ou plus)

<p>SI OUI, DEMANDER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depuis combien de temps? Si depuis plus de 7 jours, la fièvre a-t-elle été présente tous les jours? Des signes de paludisme grave? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> L'enfant émet-il des urines peu abondantes ou sèches (oca cola)? L'enfant a-t-il eu des léucorragies spontanées? Signes de troubles digestifs aigus? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Diarrhée modérée Vomissements minimes L'enfant a-t-il eu la toussote au cours des 3 derniers mois? <p>OBSERVER ET ÉCOUTER:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Une odeur de la toussote Regarder le résultat de GE+ et/ou TDR- Rechercher les signes de paludisme grave si GE+ et/ou TDR+ Urines sèches Saignement anormal États Autres signes de paludisme grave** Rechercher des signes de ROUGEOLE: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Éruption généralisée ET L'un des signes suivants: toussote, écoulement nasal, yeux rouges 	<p>Classer le PALUDISME</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tout signe phénot de danger OU Autre classification grave ou Raisons de soupçon ET GE+ et/ou TDR+ 	<p>PALUDISME GRAVE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donner de l'artémisinine en IM pour paludisme grave (première dose). Donner la première dose d'antibiotique approprié TRAITER L'enfant pour éviter l'hypoglycémie. Admettre au centre de santé, une dose de paracétamol ou d'ibuprofène si la fièvre est élevée (38°C ou plus) Revenir d'URGENCE à l'hôpital
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tout signe phénot de danger OU Raisons de soupçon ET GE+ et/ou TDR- 	<p>MALADIE FÉBRILE TRÈS GRAVE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donner la première dose d'antibiotique approprié TRAITER L'enfant pour éviter l'hypoglycémie. Admettre au centre de santé, une dose de paracétamol ou d'ibuprofène si la fièvre est élevée (38°C ou plus) Revenir d'URGENCE à l'hôpital
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fièvre (antécédents ou chaud au toucher ou température de 37.5°C ou plus) Signes de troubles digestifs aigus ET GE+ et/ou TDR+ 	<p>PALUDISME SIMPLE AVEC TROUBLES DIGESTIFS MINEURS</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donner l'artémisinine en IM/IV Admettre au centre de santé, une dose de paracétamol ou d'ibuprofène si la température est de 38°C ou plus Si arrivés des signes de troubles digestifs, continuer avec l'antipaludique de première intention pendant 3 jours Revenir l'enfant si son état ne s'améliore pas dans 24h après la prise de la première dose.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fièvre (antécédents ou chaud au toucher ou température de 37.5 °C ou plus) ET GE+ et/ou TDR- 	<p>PALUDISME SIMPLE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Donner l'antipaludique de première intention Admettre au centre de santé, une dose de paracétamol ou d'ibuprofène si la température est de 38°C ou plus. Expliquer à la mère quand revenir immédiatement. Revenir l'enfant dans 3 jours si la fièvre persiste. Si la fièvre a été présente tous les jours depuis plus de 7 jours, revenir pour bilan.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fièvre (antécédents ou chaud au toucher ou température de 37.5 °C ou plus) ET GE+ et/ou TDR- 	<p>PALUDISME PEU PROBABLE</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Admettre au centre de santé, une dose de paracétamol ou d'ibuprofène si la température est de 38°C ou plus. Donner le traitement approprié pour autres tout cause de fièvre identifiée Expliquer à la mère quand revenir immédiatement. Revenir l'enfant dans 2 jours si la fièvre persiste. Si la fièvre a été présente tous les jours depuis plus de 7 jours, revenir pour bilan.

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Age 5y-14y

Other skin lesion

Pityriasis Versicolor :
Hypo/hyperpigmented patches (most often on chest, back and arms). Not itchy

Pityriasis versicolor

- Clotrimazole 1 or 2% cream (skin)
- Pityriasis Versicolor Guidance
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Measles rash :
Red maculopapular, blanching rash.
Usually 2 to 4 days after fever, and often starts on face and spreads down. Often associated with red eyes, runny nose or cough

- Lower chest indrawing AND cough or difficulty breathing, OR
 - Tachypnea \geq 75th percentile AND cough or difficulty breathing, OR
 - Deep or extensive mouth ulcers, OR
 - Clouding of cornea, OR
 - Severe malnutrition (WFE $<$ -3 z-scores, MUAC $<$ 11.5cm, or $<$ -3 z-cores for MUAC for age in children 5-14 years), OR
 - Cerebral palsy, OR
 - HIV
- | | |
|----|-----|
| No | Yes |
|----|-----|

Non severe-measles

- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- Paracetamol
- If ulcer of mouth : Gentian violet (half strength)
- If pus draining from eye : Tetracycline eye ointment
- If $>$ 6 months and no vit. A in the past month and no RUTF : Vitamin A (Retinol)
- No referral
- Report for surveillance data
- Ttt for hypoglycemia

Severe complicated measles

- Paracetamol
- If $>$ 6 months and no vit. A in the past month and no RUTF : Vitamin A (Retinol)
- If ulcer of mouth : Gentian violet (half strength)
- If pus draining from eye : Tetracycline eye ointment
- Refer
- Report for surveillance data

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Other skin lesion

Molluscum Contagiosum:
Flesh-colored or pearly white, small papules with central umbilication. Sometimes associated with itching, not associated with fever.

Molluscum Contagiosum

- Molluscum Contagiosum guidance
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Non specific viral rash :
Many viruses cause a maculo-papular rash, they can be accompanied with unspecific symptoms such as fever, headache, muscle, joint or back pain

Non specific viral rash

- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- Paracetamol
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Head lice (Pediculosis) :
Excoriated papules and/or nits,
nymphs, lice in hair. Very itchy

Pediculosis (Head lice)

- 1st line: Benzyl benzoate emulsion (lice) |
- 2nd line: Malathion
- Advice on personal hygiene
- Lice household management advice
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Age 2m-5y

Diaper rash :
Hyperpigmented or red rash that is often itchy in the groin/buttock area due to wet diaper that has not been changed frequently

Diaper rash

1st line: Potassium permanganate solution | 2nd line: Clotrimazole 1 or 2%
- Diaper rash guidance
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Age 1y-14y

Other skin lesion

Scarlet fever:
Bright red rash that blanches with pressure, with small papules giving it a sandpaper texture (like pumice stone). It is usually located on face, neck, trunk, arms and legs; palms and soles are not involved. The spread initially starts on the neck, underarm, and groin, and then spreads over the body. The cheeks may be rosy, and a pale area around the mouth. Often associated with sore throat, abdominal pain and emesis. Typically the child presents with strawberry tongue, red tonsils with exudate or petechiae.

Scarlet Fever

Antibiotics = 1st line: Amoxicillin PO | 2nd line: Phenoxymethylpenicillin PO

- Paracetamol
- Ensure adequate fluid and calorie intake
- No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Other skin lesion

Folliculitis:
Pustules or erythematous papules anywhere hair is located, most common sites include the scalp, face, upper trunk, buttocks, legs and the underarm area. It is often itchy, and sometimes pustules can be painful. Hair shaft can frequently be seen

Extensive skin disease

No

Yes

Folliculitis

- Potassium permanganate solution
- Gentian violet
- No referral

Extensive Folliculitis

- Antibiotics = 1st line Ampicillin + Cloxacillin PO | 2nd line Erythromycin PO
- Gentian violet
 - No referral

CC4 Skin and hair symptoms

Other skin lesion

Heat rash can present as :

- Miliaria rubra : Red papules 2-4mm on a red rash. Sometimes causes itching
- Miliaria crystallina : Clear, superficial vesicles 1-2mm that look like water droplets found most often on the head, neck and upper trunk
- Caused by blocked sweat ducts, most often in newborns and those wearing tight fitted clothes

Heat rash (Miliaria crystallina/rubra)

- Heat rash guidance
- No referral

**CC5: Gastrointestinal
problem**

Age 2y-14y

- Abdominal pain, AND
(Decreased frequency of defecation, OR
Hard stool)

- No tender/colored abdominal bulge, AND
- No severe abdominal palpation needing referral, AND
- No bilious vomiting

Constipation

- Constipation counselling
- No referral

CC5: Gastrointestinal
problem

Age 2m-59m

Eating a lot less
than usual

No complicated severe acute malnutrition,
uncomplicated severe acute malnutrition, very low
weight for age, moderate acute malnutrition,
acute diarrhea, or persistent diarrhea

Loss of appetite
- Feeding counselling
- No referral

**CC5: Gastrointestinal
problem**

- Abdominal pain, OR
- <3 loose or liquid stools, OR
- Vomiting

- No severe abdominal condition, AND
- No some dehydration, AND
- No severe dehydration, AND
- No Constipation

Non-Severe abdominal condition

- Paracetamol (if abdominal pain)
- Home rehydration
- Symptomatic treatment
- No referral

**CC6: Uro-genital
problems**

- Sex male, AND
- Penile redness and/or swelling, OR
- Genital irritation or local pain

Physical exam:
- Penile redness/swelling

Balanitis

- Balanitis symptomatic care
- No referral

Rwanda Guidelines suggest antibiotic treatment:

- Prepubertal vaginitis (N.gonorrhoea, C trachomatis, T vaginalis, bacterial vaginosis -> ttt with Ceftriaxone or erythromycine if < 45 kg & <8 y ; HSV-primary infection -> acyclovir oral)
- Adolescent vulvovaginitis (T vaginalis, bacterial vaginosis) -> ttt with metronidazole, clindamycin cream; candida species (vulvovaginal candidiasis)

In our algorithm antibiotic treatment is reserved to puber girls with vaginal discharge syndrome see [specific algorithm](#)

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 12y-14y

- Sex female, AND
- Sexual contact, AND
- No fever, AND
- Abnormal vaginal discharge, AND
- No cottage-cheese-like/curdlike discharge

Vaginal Discharge Syndrome (Presumed Gonorrhea/Chlamydia/Trichomoniasis/Bacterial Vaginosis)

- Ceftriaxone IM
- Azythromycin
- Metronidazol
- Safe sex counselling
- Partner Management
- Ask for sexual abuse
- No referral

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 8y-14y

- Sex female, AND
- No fever, AND
- Abnormal vaginal discharge, AND
- Cottage-cheese-like/curdlike discharge

Vaginal Candidiasis

- Clotrimazole pessaries or topical cotrimazol cream
- No referral

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 12y-14y

- Sex female, AND
- Menarche, AND
- Sexual contact, AND
- Lower abdominal pain, AND
- Vaginal discharge, AND
- Lower abdominal tenderness

Pelvic Inflammatory Disease

- Paracetamol
- Ceftriaxone IM
- Doxycycline
- Metronidazole
- No referral
- If patient febrile refer

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 12y-14y

- Genital lesion, AND
- Genital HSV lesion

Presumed genital herpes

- Acyclovir tablets
- Safe sex counselling
- Partner management
- No referral

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 12y-14y

- Painful inguinal swelling, AND
- Sexual contact

Inguinal Bubo :
Unilateral or bilateral, tender,
sometimes purulent inguinal and/or
femoral lymphadenopathy. Develops 2-
6 weeks after painful ulcer/papules

Inguinal Bubo (LGV/Chancroid)

- Azythromycin
- Doxycycline
- Safe sex counselling
- No referral

**CC6: Uro-genital
problems**

Age 12y-14y

- Sex male, AND
- Sexual contact, AND
- Urethral discharge

**Urethral Discharge Syndrome
(Gonorrhea/Chlamydia)**

- Ceftriaxone IM
- Azythromycin
- Safe sex counselling
- Partner management
- No referral

CC6: Uro-genital problems

- Pain or difficulty urinating, AND
- NO Penile/Vaginal discharge

Pathological urine test

- Fever, OR
- Costovertebral tenderness (Age \geq 10 years)

Yes	No
-----	----

Pyelonephritis

- Antibiotics = 1st line : ciprofloxacin PO |
2nd line Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid po
- No referral
- Referral if oral intake not possible

Lower urinary tract infection

- Antibiotics = 1st line :
Co-trimoxazole PO | 2nd line
Amoxicillin/clavulanic acid po
- No referral

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 8y-14y

- Sex female, AND
- Menarche (history of menstruation), AND
- Menstruating now

- Very painful menstruation

Dysmenorrhea
- Ibuprofen
- No referral

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Age 12y-14y

- Sex female, AND
- Menarche (history of menstruation), AND
- Sexual contact , AND
- Suspicion of pregnancy

Pregnancy test

Positive

Negative

Pregnancy

- Pregnancy counselling
- Refer or seek obstetric clinic

Negative pregnancy test

- If unprotected sex more than 2 weeks ago : Safe sex counselling
- If unprotected sex within 2 weeks : consider repeating pregnancy test in 2 weeks

CC6: Uro-genital problems

Male sex

- Scrotal pain, AND
- Testicular tenderness on physical examination

Presumed testicular torsion

- Manual detorsion
- Refer urgently

- Inguinal/groin pain, or swelling, AND
- Inguinal/groin tenderness on physical examination

Inguinal hernia

- Paracetamol
- Manual reduction of hernia
- Refer for outpatient surgical evaluation (urgently if severe pain)

CC9: Prevention and screening

No known HIV+

Age
2m-14y | 12y-14y

- Unknown HIV status AND
- Mother HIV neg or unknown status

- Sexual contact, AND
- No known HIV

HIV test
Available | Not available

HIV test
positive | negative

Possible HIV
- Follow health facility protocol for confirming HIV status

Negative HIV test
- Negative HIV test - post-test counseling

HIV Screening Unavailable
- HIV Screening counseling

CC7 Neurological manifestations

Age 3y - 14y

- Headache, AND
- No Head trauma, AND
- No danger sign

Non severe Headache
- Paracetamol
- No referral

**CC8 Trauma,
accidents, burns,
pain, wounds**

**CC8 Trauma,
accidents, burns,
pain, wounds**

- Extremity pain, OR
- Joint pain, AND
- History of recent fall or trauma

Suspicion of bone fracture
or dislocation

Yes	No
-----	----

X-ray

Fracture	Dislocation	Unavailable	No fracture or dislocation
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Confirmed fracture

- Paracetamol
- Immobilize
- Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid PO if open fracture
- Urgent referral if severe pain, severe deformation, or open fracture
- Non urgent referral if no severe pain, severe deformation or open fracture
- Consider no referral in child <5 years with distal forearm fracture that is not an open fracture or severe deformation

Confirmed dislocation

- Paracetamol
- Dislocation management
- Refer if dislocation management not possible

Suspicion of clavicular fracture

Yes	No
-----	----

Suspicion of clavicular fracture

- Clavicular fracture management
- Paracetamol
- No referral

Suspicion of fracture/dislocation

- Paracetamol
- Immobilize
- Amoxicillin/Clavulanic acid PO if open fracture
- Urgent referral if severe pain, severe deformation, or open fracture
- Non urgent referral if no severe pain, severe deformation or open fracture
- Consider no referral in child <5 years with distal forearm fracture that is not an open fracture or severe deformation

Contusion

- Paracetamol
- No referral

CC8 Trauma,
accidents, burns,
pain, wounds

Burn injury

- Burn size >5% TBSA (1% = hand palm), OR
- Burn location : face, hand, other than palm,
genital area, feet, major joint, OR
- Burn circumferential

No

Yes

Minor burn

- Mupirocin cream
- Burn care
- Tetanos vaccine if not up to date
- Amoxicillin if sign of local infection
- Return every 24-48 hours to clean and dress wound

Major burn

- Mupirocin cream
- Burn care
- Tetanos vaccine if not up to date
- Amoxicillin PO if sign of local infection
- Refer

CC8 Trauma,
accidents, burns,
pain, wounds

Major car accident (pedestrian hit by fast moving car, pedestrian runover by car, passenger in car accident in fast moving car)

- Headache, OR
- Pain

Major car accident
- Refer

CC8 Trauma,
accidents, burns,
pain, wounds

- Significant exposure to fire
or smoke, OR
- Burn of the face

- Difficulty breathing, OR
- Stridor, OR
- Altered mental status

Inhalation injury

- Salbutamol INH if wheezing
- Refer

CC8 Trauma,
accidents, burns,
pain, wounds

- Major trauma (Fall from >1m for children <2 years, fall from >1.5m for children >2 years, abdomen struck by a high-impact object)

- Abdominal hematoma, OR
- Abdominal pain on palpation

Severe abdominal injury
- Paracetamol
- Refer

CC9 Prevention
and Screening

Incomplete
vaccination

Incomplete vaccination
- Complete vaccinations
- Refer to RCH

**CC9 Prevention
and Screening**

Age 1y-14y

No Mebendazole or
Albendazole in the last
6 months

Deworming

- Membendazole (deworming)
- Advise to repeat after 6 months

CC9 Prevention
and Screening

No Vit. A in the past 6 months

Vitamine A Supplementation
- vitamin A
- Advise to repeat after 6 months

CC0: General / Universal Assessment

HIV

Sickle cell

Congenital heart disease

Cerebral palsy

Severe comorbidity (HIV, Sickle cell, congenital heart disease, cerebral palsy)
- Severe comorbidity guidance for each comorbidity

2. Young infant algorithm (< 2 months)

Overview Flow

ePOCT+
Infants 1 - 59 days of life

* As per health facility standard practice

CC Chief Complaints

Generalized signs of illness (fever, convulsions, lethargy, irritable, restless)	Respiratory problem (cough, difficulty breathing, stuffed or runny nose)	Feeding problem or weight concern	Diarrhea, stool, abdominal, gastrointestinal	Skin Problem
Yes No	Yes No	Yes No	Yes No	Yes No
Jaundice (yellow skin or eyes)	Ear or mouth problem	Eye problem	Malformation or birth anomaly	Injury (birth or non-birth related)
Yes No	Yes No	Yes No	Yes No	Yes No
General/Universal Assessment and Priority Signs*				

* All items in the General/Universal Assessment are asked/evaluated of all young infants <60 days, regardless of the chief complaint(s) selected. This category is not visible to health worker to select.

CC General/Universal Assessment and CC Respiratory Complaint

RR: Respiratory rate
Abnormal body temperature: Axillary temperature ≥ 38 , OR; Axillary temperature < 35.5 .; OR Reported history of fever in present illness
VLWAZ: Very low weight for age Z-score (< -3)
LWAZ: Low weight for age Z-score (< -2)
High risk from prematurity: Birthweight < 1.5 kg OR gestational age < 34 week OR report from caregiver infant born "very early" OR "very small"
PO: Oral, HD: high dose
IMCI Fast breathing: RR ≥ 60 on two measurements, or on one measurement with 2nd infeasible

CC General/Universal Assessment
CC Yellow skin/eyes

High risk from prematurity: Gestational age <34 weeks OR birthweight <1.5 kg OR caregiver report born "Very early" OR "Very small"

Diarrhea [Evaluated in CC General/Universal assessment]

CC Diarrhea, abdominal, stool or GI

Moderate risk from prematurity: <37 weeks OR birthweight <2.5 kg OR report of baby born "early" OR "small"
High risk from prematurity: < 32 weeks OR birthweight <1.5 kg OR report of baby born "very early" OR "very small"
Diarrhea: Stools are more loose/watery than usual
PO: Oral

CC Feeding problem or low weight

* Each diagnosis/classification excludes all those listed below it

* Each diagnosis/classification excludes all those listed below it

CC Eye problem

CC General/Universal Assessment (Skin problems)

Moderate risk from prematurity: Gestational age <37 weeks OR birthweight <2.5 kg OR caregiver report born "Early" OR "Small"
High risk from prematurity: Gestational age <34 weeks OR birthweight <1.5 kg OR caregiver report born "Very early" OR "Very small"

CC Skin problems

Scabies

- 29-59 days AND
- Bumps on soles or palms, AND
- Suspicion of itch, OR
- Household members w/ itchy rashes or recent scabies diagnosis

- 5% Permethrin/Benzyl Benzoate
- Counseling on household management for scabies

Diaper rash

- 3-59 days
- Hyperpigmented or red rash in the groin/buttock area AND
- Red rash limited to groin, buttock, inner thigh area

- Topical antifungal cream (miconazole; clotrimazole)
- Counsel on diaper rash

Physiologic rash: Erythema toxicum

- 1-14 days
- Numerous red spots with small white raised spots in the middle

- Counsel that rash is not harmful and will diminish over time

Physiologic rash: Transient neonatal postural melanosis

- 1-28 days
- Small brown spots

- Counsel that rash is not harmful and will diminish over time

Mongolian spots (congenital dermal melanocytosis)

- Blue, black, grey or dark green flat spots with wavy borders and an irregular shape; often on back and buttocks, OR
- Blue, black, grey or dark green flat spots
- Present from birth

- Counsel that this is not harmful and may diminish over time

Heat rash (Miliaria crystallina/rubra)

- Very small clear, superficial vesicles 1-2 mm that look like water droplets, found most often on head, neck and upper trunk, OR
- Red papules 2-4mm on a red rash

- Counsel that rash is not harmful and how to prevent heat rash

Mastitis

- Red, swollen breast with swelling, redness limited to breast area

- IM Gentamicin and ampicillin pre-referral
- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Keep infant warm
- Refer urgent
- If referral infeasible admit

Abscess

- 7-59 days old, AND
- Red, elevated, painful skin bump, that is fluctuant

- Refer (urgent)
- IM Gentamicin and ampicillin pre-referral
- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Keep infant warm
- If referral infeasible admit
- Incise and drain if feasible

Cellulitis

- 7-59 days old, AND
- Warm, red, tender or swollen skin

- Refer (urgent)
- Prevent hypoglycemia
- Keep infant warm
- IM Gentamicin and ampicillin pre-referral
- If referral infeasible admit

CC Ear or mouth problem

CC Malformation or birth anomaly

VLWAZ: Very low weight for age Z-score (<-3)
LWAZ: Low weight for age Z-score (<-2)
High risk from prematurity: Gestational age <34 weeks OR birthweight <1.5 kg OR caregiver report born "Very early" OR "Very small"
Moderate risk from prematurity: Gestational age <37 weeks OR birthweight <2.5 kg OR caregiver report born "Early" OR "Small"

CC Injury (birth- or non-birth-related)

* Each diagnosis/classification excludes all those listed below it

Signs of infection: Redness, hot to touch, hardness, pus

HIV Risk (Assessed in CC General/Universal Assessment)

CC Vaccination (Assessed in CC General/Universal assessment)

3. Drugs linked to diagnoses

Indication	Drug	Days	Description
Abscess	Ampicillin pre-referral	1	Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, give one dose IM before referral
Abscess	Gentamicin pre-referral	1	
Abscess	Amoxicillin po	5	ANTIBIOTIC: Amoxicillin regular dose (50mg/Kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Acute diarrhea	Zinc sulfate 10 mg (half a tablet)	10	
Acute limp or joint pain	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Acute otitis media (ear infection)	Amoxicillin HD po	7	ANTIBIOTIC: amoxicillin high dose (80-100mg/kg/day divided in 2 doses), dispersible tablets
Allergic conjunctivitis	Sodium Cromoglycate 2-4% eye drops	30	
Anaphylaxis	Cetirizine po (for 6 months to 2 years)	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Anaphylaxis	Chlorpheniramine po (Piriton) (2-6 years old)	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Anaphylaxis	Chlorpheniramine po (Piriton) (6 to 12 years)	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Anaphylaxis	Cetirizine po (for >= 5 years)	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Anaphylaxis	Cetirizine po (for 2 to 5 years)	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Anaphylaxis	Epinephrine (Adrenaline) im	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Anaphylaxis	Chlorpheniramine po (Piriton) (12 to 14 years)	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Bacterial acute pharyngitis	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Bacterial acute pharyngitis	Amoxicillin po	5	Amoxicillin regular dose, dispersible tablets
Bacterial acute pharyngitis	Phenoxymethylpenicillin (Penicillin V) po	5	
Bacterial conjunctivitis	Chloramphenicol eye drops	5	
Bacterial conjunctivitis	Ciprofloxacin eye drops	5	
Bacterial conjunctivitis (< 5 y)	Chloramphenicol eye drops	5	
Bacterial conjunctivitis (< 5 y)	Ciprofloxacin eye drops	5	
Bacterial pneumonia	Erythromycin po	7	
Bacterial pneumonia	Paracetamol	3	
Bacterial pneumonia	Amoxicillin HD po	5	
Bacterial pneumonia	Amoxicillin HD po	5	
Cellulitis	Amoxicillin po	5	ANTIBIOTIC: Amoxicillin regular dose (50mg/Kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Cellulitis	Ampicillin pre-referral		
Cellulitis	Gentamicin pre-referral		
Chronic ear infection	Paracetamol	3	
Chronic ear infection	Ciprofloxacin ear drops 0.3%	14	
Chronic limp or joint pain	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
CNS Danger signs	Diazepam rectal vials (12-36m)		Pre-referral dose Give second dose if continues after 10 minutes
CNS Danger signs	Diazepam rectal vials (>= 36 months)		10mg at 10mg/2mL = 2mL Pre-referral dose Give second dose if continues after 10 minutes Use a 1 ml syringe without needle and insert it 2 to 3 cm into the rectum, or attach a nasogastric tube n°8 cut to a length of 2 to 3 cm to the tip of a 2 ml syringe. Hold the buttocks together for a few minutes.
CNS Danger signs	Diazepam rectal vials (6 - 12m)		Pre-referral dose Give second dose if continues after 10 minutes
CNS Danger signs	Phenobarbital im		
CNS Danger signs	Ampicillin HD IM/IV		High dose for severe diseases. Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
CNS Danger signs	Dextrose IV bolus		Dextrose IV for the management of hypoglycemia
CNS Danger signs	Gentamicin IM		Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
CNS Danger signs	Ceftriaxone HD IV/IM		Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
CNS Danger signs	Diazepam rectal vials (2-6m)		Pre-referral dose Give second dose if continues after 10 minutes
Common Cold	Paracetamol	3	
Complicated abscess	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Complicated abscess	Paracetamol	3	
Complicated abscess	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated acute ear infection	Amoxicillin HD po	5	ANTIBIOTIC: amoxicillin high dose (75-100mg/kg/day divided in 2 doses) If the drug is not available a prescription should be made.
Complicated acute ear infection	Paracetamol	5	
Complicated acute ear infection	Erythromycin po	5	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated cellulitis	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Complicated cellulitis	Paracetamol	5	
Complicated cellulitis	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated chicken pox	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Complicated chicken pox	Calamine lotion	5	Apply over the whole body
Complicated chicken pox	Acyclovir po (chicken pox)	5	
Complicated deep wound	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Complicated deep wound	Paracetamol	3	- Weight based dosage 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg - Four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever Oral Tablet 500mg; breakable by 2
Complicated deep wound	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated deep wound	Amoxicillin HD po	5	ANTIBIOTIC: amoxicillin high dose (75-100mg/kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Complicated impetigo	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Complicated impetigo	Fucidic acid cream 2%	7	Topical antibiotic
Complicated impetigo	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated impetigo	Paracetamol	3	
Complicated impetigo	Potassium permanganate solution 1:4000 (0.025%)	7	
Complicated neck mass	Cloxacillin po	1	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Complicated neck mass	Erythromycin po	1	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated prolonged fever	Paracetamol	3	- Weight based dosage 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg - Four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever Oral Tablet 500mg; breakable by 2
Complicated severe acute malnutrition	Gentamicin IM	1	Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day
Complicated severe acute malnutrition	Ampicillin IM	1	ANTIBIOTIC: normal dose for infection
Complicated severe acute malnutrition	Dextrose IV bolus		Dextrose IV for the management of hypoglycemia
Complicated superficial wound	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Complicated superficial wound	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Complicated superficial wound	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic: PO Amoxicillin (75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses)
Confirmed clavicular fracture	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain
Confirmed dislocation	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain
Confirmed fracture	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain

Indication	Drug	Days	Description
Confirmed fracture	Gentamicin IM	1	Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Confirmed fracture	Ampicillin IM	1	Normal dosage for infection: 200mg/kg/day Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Conjunctivitis	Tetracycline eye ointment	5	Antibacterial eye ointment
Contusion	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Corneal abrasion	Chloramphenicol eye drops	5	
Corneal abrasion	Ciprofloxacin eye drops	5	
Critical illness	Ampicillin pre-referral	1	
Critical illness	Ampicillin at facility (7 days)	7	
Critical illness	Gentamicin pre-referral	1	
Critical illness	Gentamicin at facility (7 days)	7	
Dental abscess	Metronidazole po	7	
Dental abscess	Amoxicillin po	7	
Dental abscess	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Dental abscess	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Diaper rash	Clotrimazole (diaper rash) cream 1%	14	Antifungal, Topical (skin); Cream 1%; 4 times a day Apply on affected area every 6 hours until the rash disappears, then continue for another 7 days.
Diaper rash	Clotrimazole (diaper rash) cream 1%	7	Apply on affected area every 6 hours until the rash disappears, then continue for another 7 days.
Diaper rash	Potassium permanganate solution 1:4000 (0.025%)	7	
Diarrhea with severe dehydration	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) by naso-gastric tube	1	ORS by naso-gastric tube in cases of Severe dehydration
Dysentery	Ciprofloxacin po	5	
Dysentery	Zinc sulfate 10 mg (half a tablet)	10	
Dysentery	Ciprofloxacin po [For infants less than 2 months old]	3	Antibiotic: for dysentery treatment in neonates
Dysmenorrhea	Ibuprofen po	3	As long as symptoms but max. 3 days
Eczema (Atopic dermatitis)	Betamethasone cream	14	
Eczema (Atopic dermatitis)	Hydrocortisone cream	14	
Extensive folliculitis	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Extensive folliculitis	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Extensive folliculitis	Gentian Violet (full strength) solution	5	
Extensive folliculitis	Silver sulfadiazine cream 1%	5	
Febrile urinary tract infection	Amoxicillin / clavulanic acid po	10	
Febrile urinary tract infection	Ciprofloxacin po	10	
Fever without source: presumed bacterial infection	Cotrimoxazole po	5	
Fever without source: presumed bacterial infection	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Fever without source: presumed bacterial infection	Amoxicillin HD po	5	
Fever without source: presumed bacterial infection	Ciprofloxacin po	5	
Fever without source: presumed viral illness	Paracetamol	3	
Folliculitis	Silver sulfadiazine cream 1%	5	Apply on affected areas twice a day.
Folliculitis	Gentian Violet (full strength) solution	5	
Folliculitis	Potassium permanganate solution 1:4000 (0.025%)	4	2 times a day Wet dressing with weak Potassium Permanganate soaks. Leave wet dressing for 15 to 20 minutes. Potassium permanganate solution should always be prepared fresh, as it is rapidly inactivated after being diluted.
Foreign body in ear	Ciprofloxacin ear drops 0.3%	10	
Generalized (extensive) tinea corporis	Fluconazole	42	
Generalized (extensive) tinea corporis	Griseofulvin po (for 2 months to 12 years old)	42	
Generalized (extensive) tinea corporis	Griseofulvin po (for 12 to 14 years old)	42	
Herpes simplex - Oral lesions (herpes labialis)	Acyclovir po (HSV)	5	
Herpes simplex - Oral lesions (herpes labialis)	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Hypoglycemia	Dextrose IV bolus	1	Dextrose IV bolus for the management of hypoglycemia
IMCI Anemia	Iron po	14	
IMCI/IMAI pneumonia	Amoxicillin HD po	5	Amoxicillin high dose, dispersible tablets
IMCI/IMAI pneumonia	Paracetamol	3	
IMCI/IMAI pneumonia	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Inguinal bubo (Lymphogranuloma venereum / Chancroid)	Ciprofloxacin po	3	500 mg twice daily
Inguinal bubo (Lymphogranuloma venereum / Chancroid)	Doxycycline po	14	
Inguinal hernia	Paracetamol	3	
Inhalation injury	Saibutamol INH	1	
Inhalation injury	Budesonide INH	1	Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Intestinal parasitic infection: Nematode	Albendazole po (deworming child 2 y and older)	1	Anthelmintics Dosage based on Age: >= 2 years: 400mg
Intestinal parasitic infection: Nematode	Mebendazole po (deworming)	1	Anthelmintics for routine deworming Dosage based on Age: >= 1 year : 500mg
Intestinal parasitic infection: Protozoa	Metronidazole po	7	Antibiotic: dosage 20mg/kg/dav (also used for parasitic infections)
Local skin infection	Ampiclox (Ampicillin + Cloxacillin) po syrup [For infants less than 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic for skin infection Dosing based on combined formulation 50-150mg/kg/day (equivalent to 25-75mg/kg/day for ampicillin or cloxacillin separately)
Local skin infection	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic: PO Amoxicillin (75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses)
Lower urinary tract infection (cystitis)	Amoxicillin po	3	ANTIBIOTIC: Amoxicillin regular dose (50mg/Kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Lower urinary tract infection (cystitis)	Cotrimoxazole po	3	
Lower urinary tract infection (cystitis)	Cotrimoxazole po	3	Antibiotic: dosage 8mg TMP/kg/day (dosage based on TMP)
Lower urinary tract infection (cystitis)	Amoxicillin po	3	ANTIBIOTIC: Amoxicillin regular dose (50mg/Kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Major burn	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Major burn	Fucidic acid cream 2%		Pre-referral treatment : Apply the cream before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Major burn	Silver sulfadiazine cream 1%		Pre-referral treatment : Apply the cream before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Mastitis	Ampicillin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, IM injection
Mastitis	Gentamicin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		Antibiotic: 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, IM injection
Mastitis	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic: PO Amoxicillin (75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses)
Mastitis	Cloxacillin po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic PO (For infants under 2 months old); 25-75mg/kg/day
Mastoiditis	Ampicillin IM		Ampicillin iv, powder for infection (as sodium salt), 500 mg per vial
Mastoiditis	Paracetamol	3	
Mastoiditis	Ciprofloxacin ear drops 0.3%	10	
Mastoiditis	Gentamicin IM		Gentamicin, IV, ampoule 40mg/ml in 2ml (80mg/2ml)
Mild/Moderate anemia	Iron po	14	
Minor burn	Fucidic acid cream 2%		Pre-referral treatment : Apply the cream before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Minor burn	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Minor burn	Paracetamol	5	For Pain or fever - Weight based dosing: 60-75mg/Kg/day; max daily dose: 4000mg
Minor burn	Silver sulfadiazine cream 1%	7	
Minor head injury	Paracetamol	2	
Moderate head injury	Paracetamol	3	- Weight based dosage 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg - Four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever Oral Tablet 500mg; breakable by 2

Indication	Drug	Days	Description
Moderate malnutrition	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	1	Vitamins Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU
Moderate malnutrition	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	1	Vitamin supplementation 6-12 months = 100,000 IU
Mumps	Paracetamol	5	
Neonatal conjunctivitis - (includes possible gonococcal / chlamydia infection)	Erythromycin PO [For infants less than 2 months old]	14	Antibiotic used for the treatment of chlamydial conjunctivitis. Note that there is risk of infantile hypertrophic pyloric stenosis, especially in neonates. Azithromycin is preferred for treatment of chlamydial conjunctivitis in neonates when available. Erythromycin should not be used for treatment of routine pneumonia or sepsis in neonates.
Neonatal conjunctivitis - (includes possible gonococcal / chlamydia infection)	Azithromycin po syrup [For infants less than 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic: Dosage 10mg/kg/day
Non specific viral rash	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Non-severe abdominal condition	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Non-severe headache	Paracetamol	3	
Non-severe measles	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	2	Give vitamin A dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks.
Non-severe measles	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	2	Give vitamin A dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks.
Non-severe measles	Vitamin A (retinol) for <6m	2	Vitamins - Dosage based on Age: <6 months : 50 000 IU Give vitamin A dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks.
Non-severe measles	Paracetamol	5	
Non-severe measles	Tetracycline eye ointment	14	
Non-severe measles	Gentian Violet (half strength) solution	5	
Omphalitis	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	
Omphalitis complicated / severe	Gentamicin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		
Omphalitis complicated / severe	Ampicillin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		
Omphalitis complicated / severe	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	
Oral aphthous ulcers	Gentian Violet (half strength) solution	5	
Oral aphthous ulcers	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Oral candidiasis	Nystatin (Rinse for mouth)	14	
Oral candidiasis	Fluconazole	7	
Oral candidiasis	Miconazole Gel 2% (for mouth)	14	
Oral thrush	Nystatin (Rinse for mouth)	7	
Oral thrush	Nystatin (Rinse for mouth)	7	Antifungal oral liquid 50mg/5mL (100,000iu/ml). All ages 1mL4x/day. Rinse in mouth for 3 minutes.
Orbital cellulitis	Erythromycin po		Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Orbital cellulitis	Amoxicillin HD po		ANTIBIOTIC: amoxicillin high dose (75-100mg/kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Orbital cellulitis	Cloxacillin po		50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Osteomyelitis/septic arthritis	Gentamicin IM		Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day
Osteomyelitis/septic arthritis	Ampicillin HD IM/IV		Antibiotic: High dose for severe diseases (severe pneumonia, suspicion of meningitis, CNS danger signs, very severe febrile disease, osteomyelitis/septic arthritis) = 400mg/Kg/day
Osteomyelitis/septic arthritis	Paracetamol		
Oxyuriasis (rectal symptoms/worms in stool)	Albendazole (therapeutic) po for 1-2 years	1	Single dose to be repeated once after 14 days.
Oxyuriasis (rectal symptoms/worms in stool)	Albendazole (therapeutic) po for >= 2 to 14 years	1	Single dose to be repeated once after 14 days.
Oxyuriasis (rectal symptoms/worms in stool)	Mebendazole (therapeutic) po	1	Single dose to be repeated once after 14 days.
Pediculosis (Head lice)	Permethrin 1% lotion	1	
Pediculosis (Head lice)	Benzyl Benzoate 25% Emulsion (lice) for hair	1	Apply to dry hair for 10-minutes and then rinse off with warm water. Perform second application 1 week apart.
Pelvic inflammatory disease	Paracetamol	3	
Pelvic inflammatory disease	Ceftriaxone IM for patients <46kg (STI)	1	25 to 50mg/kg (max 125mg/dose) antibiotic for STI
Pelvic inflammatory disease	Metronidazole po (STI)	14	
Pelvic inflammatory disease	Ceftriaxone IM (STI)	1	Single dose
Pelvic inflammatory disease	Doxycycline po	14	
Persistent diarrhea	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	1	Vitamins; Oral: Capsule: 50,000 IU; 100,000 IU. Oral oily solution: 100,000 IU/mL. Tablet: 10,000 IU; 50,000 IU Dosage based on Age: Age 6 - 12 months 100 000 IU 1 time a day Do not give if the child is less than 6 months, or is already on RUTF, or received vit A within the past month.
Persistent diarrhea	Zinc sulfate 10 mg (half a tablet)	10	
Persistent diarrhea	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	1	Vitamins; Oral: Capsule: 50,000 IU; 100,000 IU. Oral oily solution: 100,000 IU/mL. Tablet: 10,000 IU; 50,000 IU Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU 1 time a day Do not give if the child is already on RUTF, or received vit A within the past month.
Persisting dysentery	Azithromycin po	5	Antibiotic: Dosage 10mg/kg/day
Pityriasis versicolor	Benzoic acid compound (whitfield)	28	
Pityriasis versicolor	Clotrimazole cream	28	
Pneumonia	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	7	Antibiotic: PO Amoxicillin (75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses)
Preseptal cellulitis	Cloxacillin po	10	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Preseptal cellulitis	Erythromycin po	10	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Ka/day, max 2g/day
Presumed genital HSV	Acyclovir po (HSV)	7	
Presumed primary syphilis	Doxycycline po	14	
Presumed primary syphilis	Benzathine Penicillin i.m.	1	Single dose
Prevention and Screening	Vitamin A po (retinol) Age >=1 year	1	
Prevention and Screening	Albendazole po (deworming 1-2y)	1	
Prevention and Screening	Albendazole po (deworming child 2 y and older)	1	
Prevention and Screening	Vitamin A po (retinol) Age: 6-12m	1	
Prevention and Screening	Mebendazole po (deworming)	1	
Primary Syphilis	Benzathine Penicillin i.m.	1	Single dose
Primary Syphilis	Doxycycline po	14	
Primary Syphilis	Benzathine Penicillin i.m.	1	Single dose : Antibiotic: dosing for primary syphilis: 2.4MIU
Primary Syphilis	Doxycycline po	14	Antibiotic: Doxycycline for sexual transmitted infection 100m/dose twice a day
Pyelonephritis	Ciprofloxacin po	10	
Pyelonephritis	Ciprofloxacin po	10	Antibiotic: 20-40mg/kg/day, max 1500mg/day
Pyelonephritis	Amoxicillin / clavulanic acid po	10	ATB: weight based dosage : Amoxicillin 100mg/kg/day; min 80; max 100; max daily dose: 1.5g/d
Reactive airway disease	Budesonide INH	14	
Reactive airway disease	Salbutamol INH	14	
Scabies	Permethrin 5%	7	Apply on skin to the whole body. Permethrin should be removed by washing (bath) after 8 to 14 hours. Repeat daily for 7 days.
Scabies	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Scabies	Benzyl Benzoate Emulsion 25%	1	Apply from chin to toes and under finger nails and toenails. Leave to dry and repeat without bathing after 24 hours. Wash off on the third day. Repeat the same treatment 7 days after the last application.
Scabies	Permethrin 5%	1	Apply on skin to the whole body. Permethrin should be removed by washing (bath) after 8 to 14 hours. Apply a second application one week later.
Scarlet fever	Amoxicillin po	5	
Scarlet fever	Phenoxymethylpenicillin (Penicillin V) po	5	
Scarlet fever	Paracetamol	3	
Severe abdominal condition (possible bowel obstruction / hernia / appendicitis)	Paracetamol		

Indication	Drug	Days	Description
Severe abdominal condition (possible bowel obstruction / hernia / appendicitis)	Ciprofloxacin po		
Severe abdominal condition (possible bowel obstruction / hernia / appendicitis)	Metronidazole po		
Severe abdominal condition (possible bowel obstruction / hernia / appendicitis)	Gentamicin IM		Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day
Severe abdominal condition (possible bowel obstruction / hernia / appendicitis)	Ampicillin HD IM/IV		Antibiotic: High dose for severe diseases (severe pneumonia, suspicion of meningitis, CNS danger signs, very severe febrile disease) = 400mg/Kg/day
Severe Clinical infection or Severe illness	Gentamicin at facility (2 days)	2	
Severe Clinical infection or Severe illness	Ampicillin pre-referral	1	
Severe Clinical infection or Severe illness	Gentamicin pre-referral	1	
Severe Clinical infection or Severe illness	Amoxicillin HD po when referral infeasible/not accepted - pneumonia or severe infection (7 days)	7	
Severe complicated measles	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Severe complicated measles	Vitamin A (retinol) for <6m	2	Vitamins - Dosage based on Age: <6 months : 50 000 IU Give vitamin A dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks
Severe complicated measles	Gentamicin IM	1	Pre-referral Gentamicin
Severe complicated measles	Ampicillin IM	1	Pre-referral Ampicillin IM
Severe complicated measles	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	2	Give vitamin A dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks.
Severe complicated measles	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	2	Give vitamin A dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks.
Severe complicated measles	Tetracycline eye ointment	7	
Severe complicated measles	Gentian Violet (half strength) solution	5	Powder reconstituted to 0.25% with water *For mouth ulcers: Treating mouth ulcers controls infection and helps the child to eat. Teach the mother to treat mouth ulcers with half-strength gentian violet. Gentian violet used in the mouth should be half-strength (0.25%), not full-strength (0.5%). Give the following information. Tell the mother: • Her child will start eating normally sooner if she paints the mouth ulcers in her child's mouth. It is important that the child eats. • Clean the child's mouth. Wrap a clean soft cloth around her finger. Dip it in salt water. Wipe the mouth. • Use a clean cloth or a cotton-tipped stick to paint gentian violet on the mouth ulcers. The gentian violet will kill germs that cause the ulcers. Put a small amount of gentian violet on the cloth or stick. Do not let the child drink the gentian violet. • Treat the mouth ulcers 2 times per day, in the morning and evening. • Treat the mouth ulcers for 5 days and then stop. Wrap a clean cloth around your finger and dip it into salt water. Show the mother how to first wipe the child's mouth clean. Then paint half of the child's mouth with halfstrength gentian violet. Ask the mother to practise. Watch her wipe the child's mouth clean and paint the rest of the ulcers with gentian violet. Comment on the steps she did well and those that need to be improved. Give the mother a bottle of half-strength gentian violet to take home. Tell her to return to the clinic if the mouth ulcers get worse or if the child is not able to drink or eat. Before the mother leaves, ask checking questions. For example, ask:
Severe Croup	Dexamethasone po		
Severe Croup	Prednisolone po		
Severe dehydration	Zinc sulfate 10 mg (half a tablet)	10	Zinc for diarrhea 10mg
Severe dehydration	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) by naso-gastric tube	1	ORS by naso-gastric tube in cases of Severe dehydration
Severe eye disease	Paracetamol		On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Severe eye disease	Vitamin A (retinol) for <6m	2	Vitamins - Dosage based on Age: <6 months : 50 000 IU Give one dose on day 1 and 2, and then again in 2 weeks
Severe eye disease	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	2	Vitamin supplementation; 6-12 months = 100,000 IU Give a dose on day 1 and 2, and a third does in 2 weeks
Severe eye disease	Chloramphenicol eye drops	5	Chloramphenicol eye drops 0.50%, 1 drop every 3 hours
Severe eye disease	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	2	Vitamins: Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU Give a dose on day 1 and 2, and a third does in 2 weeks
Severe eye disease	Ciprofloxacin eye drops	5	Ciprofloxacin 0.3% eye drops
Severe malaria	Gentamicin IM		Pre-referral treatment: Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Severe malaria	Artesunate IV/IM		Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Severe malaria	Quinine IM		Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Severe malaria	Ampicillin IM		Pre-referral treatment: Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Severe malaria	Paracetamol		500mg tablet breakable in 2. Provide to patient if febrile and able to swallow
Severe Persistent Diarrhea	Zinc sulfate 10 mg (half a tablet)	14	Supplements; Oral;Dispersible tablets;20mg; breakable in 2; dosage based on Age: 2 months - 6 years: 10mg (2m-6m), 20mg (6m-6yrs)
Severe Persistent Diarrhea	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) in the clinic: WHO Treatment Plan B	1	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) for the treatment of some dehydration (WHO Treatment Plan B) in the clinic
Severe Persistent Diarrhea	Zinc sulfate 20 mg	14	Supplements; Oral;Dispersible tablets;20mg; breakable in 2; dosage based on Age: 2 months - 6 years: 10mg (2m-6m), 20mg (6m-6yrs)
Severe pneumonia	Gentamicin IM		Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day
Severe pneumonia	Paracetamol		
Severe pneumonia	Ampicillin HD IM/IV		
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Gentamicin pre-referral		Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, 1 IM injection before referral
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Gentamicin IM [For infants under 2 months old]	2	Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, IM injection
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Ampicillin pre-referral	1	Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, give one dose IM before referral
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	7	Antibiotic : 75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses per day
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Ampicillin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, IM injection
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Gentamicin IM [For infants under 2 months old]	1	Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, IM injection
Severe pneumonia or Severe respiratory illness	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	7	Antibiotic : 75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses per day
Severe skin infection	Ampiclox (Ampicillin + Cloxacillin) po syrup [For infants less than 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic for skin infection Dosing based on combined formulation 50-150mg/kg/day (equivalent to 25-75mg/kg/day for ampicillin or cloxacillin separately)
Severe skin infection	Ampicillin + cloxacillin IM (Ampiclox) [For infants under 2 months old] (Pre-Referral)		100mg/kg 3 times per day if age > 7 days
Severe skin infection	Ampiclox IM pre-referral for <= 7 days of age		100mg/kg 2 times per day if <= 7 days of age
Severe skin infection	Ampicillin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		Antibiotic: IM 50 mg/kg/dose
Severe skin infection	Gentamicin IM [For infants under 2 months old]		Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose
Severe skin infection	Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	5	Antibiotic : 75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses per day
Severe skin infection	Ampicillin pre-referral		Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, give one dose IM before referral
Simple abscess	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Simple abscess	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Simple febrile convulsion	Paracetamol	3	
Some dehydration	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) in the clinic: WHO Treatment Plan B	1	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) for the treatment of some dehydration (WHO Treatment Plan B) at the health facility

Indication	Drug	Days	Description
Suspected malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight >=35kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: >=35kg: 4 tablets twice a day
Suspected malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight <15kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: 5-<15 kg: 1 tablet twice a day
Suspected malaria	Artesunate IV/IM	3	Pre-referral anti-Malarial for severe malaria Weightbased dosage: >20 kg : 2.4mg/kg/day <20 kg : 3mg/kg/day
Suspected malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight 15 to <25kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: 15-30 kg: 2 tablets twice a day
Suspected malaria	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Suspected malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight 25 to <35kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: 25 to <35kg: 3 tablets twice a day
Suspected severe malaria	Quinine IM		Anti-malarial: Quinine, IM; Weightbased loading dosage: 20 mg/Kg one dose for Pre-referral
Suspected severe malaria	Ampicillin IM		Pre-referral antibiotic
Suspected severe malaria	Gentamicin IM		Normal dosage for infection: 200mg/kg/day
Suspected severe malaria	Artesunate IV/IM		Gentamicin, IM, ampoule 40mg/ml in 2ml (80mg/2ml)
Suspected severe malaria	Artesunate IV/IM		Anti-Malarials: IV/IM: Injection: 60mg or 120mg vial of anhydrous artesunic acid with a separate ampoule of 5% sodium bicarbonate solution; Weightbased dosage: 2.4mg/kg/day Pre-referral dose
Suspected severe malaria	Paracetamol		- Weight based dosage 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg - Four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for fever
Suspected testicular torsion	Paracetamol		Duration : Pre-referral - Weight based dosage 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg - Four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever Oral Tablet 500mg; breakable by 2
Suspicion of fracture/dislocation	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain
Suspicion of fracture/dislocation	Ampicillin IM		
Suspicion of fracture/dislocation	Gentamicin IM		Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day Pre-referral treatment : Give the first dose of the medication before referring the child. The full duration of the treatment will be prescribed at the referral health facility.
Suspicion of meningitis	Gentamicin IM		
Suspicion of meningitis	Ampicillin HD IM/IV		
Tinea capitis	Fluconazole	42	
Tinea capitis	Griseofulvin po (for 12 to 14 years old)	42	
Tinea capitis	Griseofulvin po (for 2 months to 12 years old)	42	
Tinea corporis	Clotrimazole cream	28	
Tinea corporis	Benzoic acid compound (whitfield)	28	
Tooth pain	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Typhoid Fever	Paracetamol	3	For Pain or fever - Weight based dosing: 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg
Typhoid Fever	Azithromycin po	7	Antibiotic: Dosage 10mg/kg/day
Typhoid Fever	Ciprofloxacin po	10	Antibiotic: 20-40mg/kg/day, max 1500mg/day
Uncomplicated acute ear infection	Paracetamol	3	
Uncomplicated cellulitis	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Uncomplicated cellulitis	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Uncomplicated cellulitis	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Uncomplicated chicken pox	Calamine lotion	5	Apply over the whole body
Uncomplicated chicken pox	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Uncomplicated deep wound	Paracetamol	3	- Weight based dosage 80mg/Kg/day (min dose per kg/day 60; max dose per kg/day 80); max daily dose: 4000mg - Four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever Oral Tablet 500mg; breakable by 2
Uncomplicated impetigo	Fucidic acid cream 2%	7	Topical antibiotic
Uncomplicated impetigo	Potassium permanganate solution 1:4000 (0.025%)	5	
Uncomplicated infectious lymphadenitis	Erythromycin po	7	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day
Uncomplicated infectious lymphadenitis	Cloxacillin po	7	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day
Uncomplicated infectious lymphadenitis	Paracetamol	3	
Uncomplicated lymphadenopathy	Paracetamol	3	
Uncomplicated Malaria	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Uncomplicated Malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight 25 to <35kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: 25 to <35kg: 3 tablets twice a day
Uncomplicated Malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight <15kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: 5-<15 kg: 1 tablet twice a day
Uncomplicated Malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight >=35kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: >=35kg: 4 tablets twice a day
Uncomplicated Malaria	Artesunate IV/IM	1	Weight based dosage: >20 kg : 2.4mg/kg/day <20 kg : 3mg/kg/day
Uncomplicated Malaria	Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight 15 to <25kg)	3	Give the first dose at the clinic and observe for one hour. If the child vomits within an hour repeat the dose. Give second dose at home after 8 HOURS. Then twice daily for further two days. Artemether-lumefantrine should be taken with food. Nb of tablet according to body weight: 15-30 kg: 2 tablets twice a day
Uncomplicated severe acute malnutrition	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	1	Vitamin supplementation 6-12 months = 100,000 IU
Uncomplicated severe acute malnutrition	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	1	Vitamins Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU
Uncomplicated severe acute malnutrition	Amoxicillin po	5	ANTIBIOTIC: Amoxicillin regular dose (50mg/Kg/day divided in 2 doses)
Uncomplicated severe acute malnutrition	Cotrimoxazole po	5	Antibiotic: dosage 8mg TMP/kg/day (dosage based on TMP)
Urethral discharge syndrome (Gonorrhoea / Chlamydia)	Doxycycline po	7	Antibiotic: Doxycycline for sexual transmitted infection 100mg/dose twice a day
Urethral discharge syndrome (Gonorrhoea / Chlamydia)	Ceftriaxone IM for patients <46kg (STI)	1	25 to 50mg/kg (max 125mg/dose) antibiotic for STI
Urethral discharge syndrome (Gonorrhoea / Chlamydia)	Ceftriaxone IM (STI)	1	Single dose

Indication	Drug	Days	Description
Urticaria	Cetirizine po (for >= 5 years)	3	
Urticaria	Chlorpheniramine po (Pirton) (2-6 years old)	3	
Urticaria	Cetirizine po (for 6 months to 2 years)	3	
Urticaria	Cetirizine po (for 2 to 5 years)	3	
Urticaria	Chlorpheniramine po (Pirton) (6 to 12 years)	3	
Urticaria	Chlorpheniramine po (Pirton) (12 to 14 years)	3	
Vaginal candidiasis	Clotrimazole (genital) cream 1%	6	Topical (vuvovaginal)
Vaginal candidiasis	Fluconazole po (vaginal candidiasis)	1	Single dose
Vaginal discharge syndrome (Presumed Gonorrhea/Chlamydia / Trichomoniasis / Bacterial Vaginosis)	Doxycycline po	7	Antibiotic: Doxycycline for sexual transmitted infection 100mg/dose twice a day
Vaginal discharge syndrome (Presumed Gonorrhea/Chlamydia / Trichomoniasis / Bacterial Vaginosis)	Metronidazole po (STI)	7	
Vaginal discharge syndrome (Presumed Gonorrhea/Chlamydia / Trichomoniasis / Bacterial Vaginosis)	Ceftriaxone IM (STI)	1	Single dose
Vaginal discharge syndrome (Presumed Gonorrhea/Chlamydia / Trichomoniasis / Bacterial Vaginosis)	Ceftriaxone IM for patients <46kg (STI)	1	25 to 50mg/kg (max 125mg/dose) antibiotic for STI
Very low weight for age	Amoxicillin po	5	
Very low weight for age	Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	1	Vitamins Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU
Very low weight for age	Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	1	Vitamin supplementation 6-12 months = 100,000 IU
Very low weight for age	Cotrimoxazole po	5	
Very severe febrile disease	Diazepam rectal vials (12-36m)	1	Pre-referral anticonvulsant Age based dosing: 12-36m: 1.5 mL
Very severe febrile disease	Ampicillin HD IM/IV	1	Duration: Pre-referral = 1 day Antibiotic: High dose for severe diseases (severe pneumonia, suspicion of meningitis, CNS danger signs, very severe febrile disease) = 400mg/Kg/day
Very severe febrile disease	Phenobarbital im	1	Pre-referral duration: 1 day Anti-convulsant Weight based dosage: 20 mg/Kg
Very severe febrile disease	Diazepam rectal vials (>= 36 months)	1	Pre-referral anticonvulsant Age based dosing: >=36m: 2 mL
Very severe febrile disease	Diazepam rectal vials (6 - 12m)	1	Pre-referral anti-convulsant Age 6-12 months = 5mg
Very severe febrile disease	Diazepam rectal vials (2-6m)	1	Anti-convulsant: Age 2-6 months = 2.5mg
Very severe febrile disease	Gentamicin IM	1	Pre-referral = 1 day Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day
Viral acute pharyngitis	Paracetamol	3	On demand, max four times a day (roughly every 6hrs) as needed for pain or fever
Viral pneumonia	Paracetamol	3	
Vulvovaginitis	Metronidazole po	7	Metronidazole tablets 200ma/ suspension 200mg/5ml, dosage 20mq/kq/day

4. Drug formulations

Label	Formulation
Acyclovir po (HSV)	Antiviral for HSV: dosage based on weight: 80mg/kg/day; daily maximum dose 1200mg. 400mg tablet 200mg tablet
Acyclovir po (chicken pox)	Antiviral for chicken pox: dosage based on weight: 80mg/kg/day; daily maximum dose 3200mg. 200mg tablet 400mg tablet
Albendazole (therapeutic) po for 1-2 years	Anti-helminthics for oxyuriasis Dosage based on Age; for 1-2 years: 200mg 400mg tablet 200mg tablet
Albendazole (therapeutic) po for >= 2 to 14 years	Anti-helminthics for oxyuriasis Dosage based on Age; for 2-14 years: 400mg 400mg tablet 200mg tablets
Albendazole po (deworming 1-2y)	200mg tablet 400mg tablet
Albendazole po (deworming child 2 y and older)	400mg tablet 200mg tablet
Amoxicillin po	Antibiotic: Amoxicillin regular dose (50mg/Kg/day divided in 2 doses) 250mg dispersible tablet 125mg dispersible tablet 125mg/5ml syrup
Amoxicillin HD po when referral infeasible/not accepted - pneumonia or severe infection (7 days)	Antibiotic : 75-100 mg/kg/day, give twice a day for 7 days Dispersible tablet 125 mg Dispersible tablet 250 mg Syrup 125 mg/5 ml
Amoxicillin HD po [For infants under 2 months old]	Antibiotic: PO Amoxicillin (75-100 mg/kg/day, divided in two doses) 250mg dispersible tablet 125mg/5ml syrup 125mg dispersible tablet
Amoxicillin HD po	Antibiotic: amoxicillin high dose (75-100mg/kg/day divided in 2 doses) 125mg/5ml syrup 125mg Dispersible Tablet 250mg dispersible tablet
Amoxicillin / clavulanic acid po	Antibiotic: weight based dosage : Amoxicillin 100mg/kg/day; min 80; max 100; max daily dose: 1.5g/d Amoxicillin 500mg + Clavulanic acid 125mg Syrup: 125mg amoxicillin + 31.5mg clavulanic acid / 5mL
Ampicillin at facility (7 days)	Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, give twice a day during 7 days at facility Vial of 250 mg Vial of 500 mg
Ampicillin pre-referral	Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, give one dose IM before referral Vial of 500mg Vial of 250 mg
Ampicillin HD IM/IV	500mg/2.5mL vial: powder for infection (as sodium salt)
Ampicillin IM	Antibiotic Normal dosage for infection: 200mg/kg/day 500mg/2.5mL vial: powder for injection (as sodium salt)
Ampicillin IM [For infants under 2 months old]	Antibiotic: 50 mg/kg/dose, IM injection IM - 500mg vial: powder for injection IM - 250mg vial: powder for injection
Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight >=35kg)	20 mg artemether/120 mg lumefantrine tablet
Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight >=35kg)	80 mg artemether/480 mg lumefantrine tablet
Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight <15kg)	20 mg artemether/120 mg lumefantrine tablet
Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight 15 to <25kg)	20 mg artemether/120 mg lumefantrine tablet
Artemether-Lumefantrine po (Weight 25 to <35kg)	20 mg artemether/120 mg lumefantrine tablet
Artesunate IV/IM	Pre-referral anti-Malarial for severe malaria Weightbased dosage: 2.4mg/kg/day 60mg vial for IM injection 120mg vial for IM injection 120mg vial for IV injection 60mg vial for IV injection
Azithromycin po syrup [For infants less than 2 months old]	Antibiotic: Dosage 10mg/kg/day 125mg/5mL syrup
Azithromycin po	Antibiotic: Dosage 10mg/kg/day 125mg/5mL syrup 250mg tablet 500mg tablet
Benzoic acid compound (whitfield)	Antifungal topical ointment for tinea corporis or pityriasis versicolor 3 or 6% ointment
Benzyl Benzoate 25% Emulsion (lice) for hair	Lotion for head lice 25% emulsion
Benzathine Penicillin i.m.	Antibiotic: dosing for primary syphilis: 2.4MIU 5mL vial of 2.4 MIU
Benzyl Benzoate Emulsion 25%	Emulsion for scabies Benzyl benzoate 25% emulsion
Betamethasone cream	Topical Steroids for eczema (atopic dermatitis) 0.1% ointment
Budesonide INH	Inhalators for reactive airway disease (asthma) or inhalation injury with wheeze 200mcg inhaler 100mcg inhaler
Calamine lotion	Anti-inflammatory or Antipruritic Preparations for chicken pox or other skin condition Calamine lotion
Ceftriaxone IM (STI)	Antibiotic: Ceftriaxone IM for Sexually transmitted infection Dosage 500mg/dose/day IM - 250mg/mL vial
Ceftriaxone IM for patients <46kg (STI)	25 to 50mg/kg (max 125mg/dose) antibiotic for STI IM - 250mg/ml

Label	Formulation
Ceftriaxone HD IV/IM	Antibiotic: Ceftriaxone HD for severe infection (meningitis, danger signs): 80mg/Kg, max 4g/day 250mg powder for injection in vial
Cetirizine po (for >= 5 years)	Anti-histamine Dosage by Age; age >= 5 years 10mg 10mg tablet
Cetirizine po (for 6 months to 2 years)	Anti-histamine Dosage by Age; Age 6m - 2 years: 2.5mg 5mg/5mL Syrup
Cetirizine po (for 2 to 5 years)	Anti-histamine Dosage by Age; Age 2 to 5 years: 5mg 10mg tablet
Chlorpheniramine po (Piriton) (12 to 14 years)	Anti-histamine Age 12-14 years: 4 mg 4 times a day; daily max dosage: 16mg
Chlorpheniramine po (Piriton) (2-6 years old)	Anti-histamine Age 2-6 years: 2mg 2 times a day; daily max dosage: 4mg 4mg tablet
Chlorpheniramine po (Piriton) (6 to 12 years)	Anti-histamine Age 6-12 years: 2 mg 3 times a day; daily max dosage : 6mg 4mg tablet
Chloramphenicol eye drops	Antibiotic eye drops Chloramphenicol eye drops 0.50%
Ciprofloxacin eye drops	Ciprofloxacin 0.3% eye drops 0.3% eye drops
Ciprofloxacin po	Antibiotic: 20-40mg/kg/day, max 1500mg/day Oral liquid 250mg / 5 ml 500mg tablet
Ciprofloxacin ear drops 0.3%	250mg tablet Ear drops for ear infection Ciprofloxacin ear drops 0.3%
Ciprofloxacin po [For infants less than 2 months old]	Antibiotic: PO 30 mg/kg/day for young infants Oral liquid 250mg / 5 ml
Clotrimazole (diaper rash) cream 1%	Antifungal for diaper rash Cream 1%
Clotrimazole (genital) cream 1%	Antifungal cream for vaginal candidiasis Cream 1%
Clotrimazole cream	Antifungal cream for tinea corporis or pityriasis versicolor 1 or 2 % cream
Cloxacillin po	50 to 100 mg/kg/day, max 4g/day 125mg/5ml syrup
Cloxacillin po [For infants under 2 months old]	Antibiotic PO (For infants under 2 months old): 25-75mg/kg/day 125mg/5ml Syrup
Cotrimoxazole po	Antibiotic: dosage 8mg TMP/kg/day (dosage based on TMP) Tablet 480mg (Trimethoprim 80mg, Sulfamethoxazole 400mg) Syrup: 240mg / 5mL = 40mg Trimpethoprim; 200mg Sulfamethoxazole
Dexamethasone po	2mg tablet 0.5mg tablet
Dextrose IV bolus	Dextrose IV for the management of hypoglycemia Dextrose 5% Dextrose 10%
Diazepam rectal vials (12-36m)	Pre-referral anticonvulsant Age based dosing: 12-36m: 1.5 mL
Diazepam rectal vials (12-36m)	10mg/2mL ampoule
Diazepam rectal vials (>= 36 months)	Pre-referral anticonvulsant Age based dosing: >=36m: 2 mL
Diazepam rectal vials (>= 36 months)	10mg/2mL ampoule
Diazepam rectal vials (6 - 12m)	Pre-referral anti-convulsant Age 6-12 months = 5mg 10mg/2mL ampoule
Diazepam rectal vials (2-6m)	Anti-convulsant: Age 2-6 months = 2.5mg 10mg/2mL ampoule
Doxycycline po	Antibiotic: Doxycycline for sexual transmitted infection 100mg/dose twice a day 100mg tablet
Epinephrine (Adrenaline) im	Sympathomimetic for anaphylaxis Weight based dosage 0.01mL/Kg;max 0.3mg 1mg/mL ampoule
Erythromycin po	Antibiotic: 50 mg/Kg/day, max 2g/day 250mg tablet 125mg/5mL syrup
Erythromycin PO [For infants less than 2 months old]	Antibiotic used for the treatment of chlamydial conjunctivitis. Note that there is risk of infantile hypertrophic pyloric stenosis, especially in neonates. Azithromycin is preferred for treatment of chlamydial conjunctivitis in neonates when available. Erythromycin should not be used for treatment of routine pneumonia or sepsis in neonates.
Fluconazole	Antifungal for tinea corporis, tinea capitis, and oral candidiasis Dosage based on Weight; 6mg/Kg/day; maximum 200mg/day 150mg tablet 50mg/5mL suspension 50mg capsule
Fluconazole po (vaginal candidiasis)	2nd line antifungal for vaginal candidiasis Age 8-14 years: 150mg 50mg capsule 150mg capsule
Fucidic acid cream 2%	Topical antibiotic 2% cream
Gentamicin at facility (7 days)	Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, IM injection once a day during 7 days at facility Vial of 80 mg/2ml Vial of 20 mg/ml Vial of 10mg/ml

Label	Formulation
Gentamicin pre-referral	Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, 1 IM injection before referral
	Vial of 80 mg/2ml
	Vial of 20 mg/ml
	Vial of 10mg/ml
Gentamicin IM [For infants under 2 months old]	Antibiotic, 5-7.5 mg/kg/dose, IM injection
	IM - 40mg/2ml ampoule (20 mg/ml)
	IM - 80mg/2ml ampoule (40 mg/ml)
	IM - 20mg/2ml ampoule (10 mg/ml)
Gentamicin IM	Antibiotic: 7mg/Kg/day, max 400mg/day
	80mg/2mL ampoule
	20mg/2ml ampoule
	40mg/2ml ampoule
Gentian Violet (full strength) solution	Anti-infective solution for Folliculitis
	Powder reconstituted to 0.5% with water
Gentian Violet (half strength) solution	Anti-infective solution for mouth ulcers
	Half-strength (0.25%)
	Ampicillin 125mg + Cloxacillin 125mg = 250mg/5mL syrup
Griseofulvin po (for 2 months to 12 years old)	Antifungal for tinea corporis or tinea capitis
	Dosage based on Weight + age; Age 2m - 12 years : 20mg/Kg (15-25mg/kg) daily max 500mg
	500mg tablet
	250mg tablet
Griseofulvin po (for 12 to 14 years old)	Antifungal for tinea corporis and capitis
	Dosage based on age; Age 12-14 years : 500mg
	250mg tablet
	500mg tablet
	4mg tablet
Hydrocortisone cream	Topical Steroids for eczema (atopic dermatitis)
	0.5% acetate cream
	1% ointment (base)
Ibuprofen po	Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drugs (NSAID)
	Dosage based on Weight : 30mg/kg (15-30mg/kg/day)
	400mg tablet
	200mg tablet
Iron po	Ferrous sulfate syrup 20 mg/mL
Iron po	Tablet: Iron 60mg (Fe Sulfate 200mg + vit B9 2.5mg)
Mebendazole (therapeutic) po	Anti-helminthics treatment for oxyuriasis
	100mg/5mL
	100mg tablet
Mebendazole po (deworming)	Anthelmintics for routine deworming
	Dosage based on Age: >=1 year : 500mg
	100mg tablet
	100mg/5mL
	500mg tablet
Metronidazole po (STI)	Antibiotic: Metronidazole, dosage for sexual transmitted disease, 400mg/dose twice a day
	200mg tablet
Metronidazole po	Antibiotic: dosage 20mg/kg/day
	200mg/5mL Suspension
	200mg tablet
Miconazole Gel 2% (for mouth)	Antifungal for oral candidiasis Dosage based on Age;
	- For 2 months to 2 years : 1.25 ml
	- For over 2 years and adult 2.5 ml
	2% topical gel
Nystatin (Rinse for mouth)	Antifungal for oral candidiasis and thrush
	50mg/5ml (100,000IU/ml)
	For All ages: 1mL 4 times per day
Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) in the clinic: WHO Treatment Plan B	Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) for the treatment of some dehydration (WHO Treatment Plan B) in the clinic
	Sachet of ORS (20.5g)
Oral Rehydration Salts (ORS) by naso-gastric tube	ORS by naso-gastric tube in cases of Severe dehydration
	Sachet of ORS (20.5g)
Paracetamol	For Pain or fever
	- Weight based dosing: 60-75mg/Kg/day; max daily dose: 4000mg
	500mg tablet
	125mg/5mL syrup
	100mg tablet
	Paracetamol suppository 125mg
Permethrin 1% lotion	Permethrin 1% lotion
Permethrin 5%	Permethrin 5% cream
Phenobarbital im	Anti-convulsant
	Weight based dosage: 20 mg/Kg
Phenoxyethylpenicillin (Penicillin V) po	Antibiotic: dosage 100mg/kg/day
	125mg/5mL Suspension
	250mg tablet
Potassium permanganate solution 1:4000 (0.025%)	Anti-infective for skin rashes (diaper rash, impetigo, folliculitis)
	Solution: 1:4000 (0.025%)
Prednisolone po	5mg tablet
	5mg/5mL syrup
	50m/5 mL (100,000 IU/mL) suspension
Quinine IM	2nd line Anti-malarial treatment for severe malaria
	Weight based loading dose: 20 mg/Kg
	300mg/ml quinine hydrochloride in 2mL ampoule
Salbutamol INH	Inhalator for reactive airway disease (asthma) or inhalation injury with wheeze
Silver sulfadiazine cream 1%	Anti-infective topical cream for burns and folliculitis
	Cream 1%
Sodium Cromoglycate 2-4% eye drops	Anti-inflammatory eye drops for conjunctivitis
	Dosage based on Age; For 4 - 12 years : 1 drop q6h
	Sodium Cromoglycate 2% or 4%
Tetracycline eye ointment	Antibacterial eye ointment
	Tetracycline eye ointment

Label	Formulation
Vitamin A po (retinol) Age >=1 year	Vitamin
	Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU
	50,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
	100,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
	50,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
	100,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
Vitamin A po (retinol) Age: 6-12m	100,000 IU/mL Solution
	200,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
	Vitamin supplementation
	6-12 months = 100,000 IU
	100,000 IU capsule
	50,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
Vitamin A (retinol) for <6m	50,000 IU capsule
	100,000 IU/mL solution
	50mg/mL Suspension
	Vitamins - Dosage based on Age: <6 months : 50 000 IU
	50,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
	100,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
Vitamin A po (retinol) for 6 to 12 months of age	50,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
	100,000 IU/mL Solution
	Vitamin supplementation
	6-12 months = 100,000 IU
	50,000 IU capsule
	50,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
Vitamin A po (retinol) for >= 1 year of age	100,000 IU/mL solution
	100,000 IU capsule
	Vitamins
	Dosage based on Age: >= 1 years :200 000 IU
	100,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
	50,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
Zinc sulfate 10 mg (half a tablet)	100,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
	200,000 IU capsule (as palmitate)
	100,000 IU/mL Solution
	50,000 IU tablet (as palmitate)
	Zinc for diarrhea
	10mg
Zinc sulfate 20 mg	20mg dispersible tablet
	Zinc for diarrhea
	20mg tablet